

THE ATTENTION WHICH PAID TO THE STUDY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN OUR COUNTRY IN RECENT YEARS AND USING INNOVATION TECHNOLOGIES FOR THIS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6367573>

Barotaliyeva Muyassar Murodaliyevna

The first-year student of Termez State University, a faculty of foreign philology

Annotation: *The article discuss the attention to the foreign languages, the effectiveness of innovative technologies and way for easy language learning. Then give the information of the role of innovative technologies in improving learning skills. In this days besides receiving foreign languages then native language have become extremely beneficial. So that modern technologies are great help to us.*

Keywords: *contemporary technologies, social network, knowledge, experiment testing, different apps, a computer, self education, education system.*

In this days, one of the main requirements for a high-ranking profession is a perfect knowledge of foreign languages. It is no coincidence that at present, our country pays special attention to the study of languages, which are among the leading languages of international communication. The education system of Republic of Uzbekistan is rising to a new level of quality on the basis of the introduction of new information and communication technologies, besides, pedagogical technologies that are designed to teach and learn languages that can fully meet the requirements of the time. In addition, special attention is paid to any research in in-depth study of foreign languages in higher education. In the process of training specialists, it is important to ensure the priority of the education system, including the introduction of the new technologies and mechanisms in the study of foreign languages. It is well known that the expression of thought, the connection between people, spiritually and other relations are manifested through language. So there is a growing focus on this. Then the reflection of modern technologies in the education system will increase the level of foreign language teaching and learning. An increase in number off staff who can communicate in different languages is a guarantee of achieving positive results in the field of education. With the rapid development of information and communication technologies, which is one of the peculiarities of our time, special attention is paid to a new approach to the educational process and its organization, using its potential. The XXI century is

a century of high technologies and our modern youth is not only in line with the spirit of the times, but also in line with the development of the electronic world. Therefore, many changes are taking place in the field of education. Nowadays, lessons focus more on students' independent research, with the teachers primarily acting as facilitators. A teacher and students who keep pace with the times should be prepared to enliven any part of the lesson with a variety of technologies. New information technologies offer great opportunities in teaching and learning a foreign language, play an important role in obtaining quality knowledge in science and increasing the effectiveness of education. It is known that according to the requirements of the time, none of the foreign language classes should be held without presentation. The focus on technological advancement began to develop a few years ago. The resolution of the first President Islam Karimov states that "the system of teaching the younger generation in foreign language through the introduction of advanced methods of teaching, using modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies, the training of specialists fluent in these languages to radically improve and on this basis to create opportunities for their achievements in world development and the wider use of world information recourses, the development of international cooperation and dialogue" and for this the need to perform a number of important tasks. Then from the first grade of general secondary schools, foreign languages were taught in the form of games and that of as a basic educational subject, using modern technologies. In line with such important decisions, a more in-depth look was taken at foreign language learning classes in particular. In order to properly defend the honor of the country on the world stage, our youth must first be able to compete with their foreign peers. Today, such competitions are held especially in English, which is an international business language.

ICT tools – computer technology, tape recorders, video equipment, electronic whiteboard and others are a productive method and save the learners' time. In addition, any information related to science can be easily found on the google internet network. Apart from this, one of the most useful ways is now for the student to independently perform a variety of quiz tests to consolidate and improve their knowledge. Today, young people do not spend time searching and browsing a book for more information, but turn on the internet to save it. As a result of the use of the internet and its great potential in the teaching of foreign languages, the prospects for the introduction of multimedia technologies in the educational and pedagogical processes are becoming increasingly clear.

It is known that, acquaintance with the internet as the main means of communication is in several directions:

- *internet as a means of obtaining information;
- *internet as a communication tool;
- *internet is done as a means of entertainment;

Several didactic issues can be addressed through the use of internet in foreign language classes. With that students can check their knowledge:

- *various online tests, namely interactive mode of tests;
- *offline tests namely use of electronic version of tests;
- *in the internet system there are many tests like Toefl and Ielts for students from elementary to advanced level of knowledge. The advantage of such test for the reader is in the objective and rapid response. Therefore, different tests may be given to students with different levels at the same time.

The use of photos, clips, videos in explaining a new topic will help you to quickly and easily master the subject. Technologies benefit every aspect of language learning. For instance, for listening of course, it is impossible to perform this process without a computer, a player or cd. Listening is one of the significant parts of language learning. It requires the reader to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammar rules, vocabulary and meanings at the same time. That of, to develop speaking skills, it is effective to watch various performances, movies and cartoons in the same language. By that we can speak other languages like native speaker, because with the native videos we can feel the atmosphere. We can not imagine our studies without contemporary technologies. People always must see and use the beneficial sides of everything. These make the learning process quite interesting.

REFERENCES:

1. <http://uz.infocom.uz>
2. <http://cyberleninka.uz>
3. <https://www.crunchbase.com>

